

De Dea Syria

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Entry tags: Hellenistic Religions, Religious Group, Text, Ancient Greek text, Greek Religions, Hellenistic Neo-Paganism, Mesopotamian Religions, Phoenician Cult, Assyrian Religions, Babylonian Religions, Aramaic Religions, Canaanite Religions, Near East, Phrygia, Egyptian Religions, Mystery Religion, Ancient Syrian Religion

De Dea Syria is a text attributed to Lucian which describes the mythology and worship of the goddess Atargatis in the Syrian city of Hieropolis, as well as the temple dedicated to her and the legends surrounding it. It begins with a discussion of the rites of Astarte practiced in nearby Byblos, before turning its gaze to Hieropolis and the origins of its ancient temple through a retelling of the Atra-Hasis flood myth where the deluge is drained through a cleft in the rock beneath the sanctuary, and going on to state that others aver that it was founded by Semiramis in honor of her mother, the aquatic goddess Dir keto, or by a certain Attes in honor of Rhea, or, alternately, as a site of Bacchic worship. The construction of the current iteration of the sanctuary is attributed to a certain Kombabos who castrated himself as a way to cure himself of his attraction to his stepmother (an occurrence connected to the rites of self-castration practiced by the Galli). Finally, the temple itself is described as being an ionic building replete with statues, xoana, ritual implements, sanctified pools and flocks of sacred animals. The diverse rites practiced within the temple are also enumerated, including the animal sacrifices and ecstatic rites which characterize worship at the site, as well as the dedications made to it by the inhabitants of the regions (indeed the author states that he himself dedicated the first growth of his beard to the temple as was the custom among Syrian youths and maidens) It might also be argued to constitute an early work of cultural anthropology or comparative religion, owing to its focus on the origins of particular rites and rituals practiced at Hieropolis and the similarities (and, indeed, common origins) of these ceremonies with the practices of other antique cultures, often making comparison with wider Hellenistic religious culture. It is written in a Herodotean Ionic style, and implicitly references Herodotean notions of historiography and narrative. The nature of the religious pageantry attached to the temple complex is also described in detail, imparting a sense of the nature of Syrian religious practice at the beginning of Late Antiquity.

Date Range: 150 CE - 250 CE

Region: Roman Syria

Region tags: Syria, Eastern Mediterranean, Levant, Ancient Rome

Roman Syria, A.D. 200 Byzantium, A.D. 400-1453

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: J.L. Lightfoot (2003), *Lucian On the Syrian Goddess: Edited with Introduction, Translation and Commentary*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

– Source 2: Dirven, Lucinda. “The Author of ‘De Dea Syria’ and His Cultural Heritage.” *Numen*, vol. 44, no. 2, 1997, pp. 153–79. JSTOR, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/3270297>. Accessed 8 May 2023.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: N/A

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: N/A

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Other textile: Parchment

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– I don't know

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– I don't know

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The circulation of the text is largely unclear.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– I don't know

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It has traditionally been ascribed to Lucian and placed within his corpus of works, though this has been debated. It does not possess direct relationship with any of his other works, but has been transmitted alongside them.

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Comparative Religion, Cultural Anthropology, Ethnography

Notes: The author provides a Herodotean religious ethnography of the complex at Hieropolis, which has overtones of antiquarianism and anthropological study, as well as potential satire and humor characteristic of Lucian's work.

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

–Other [specify]: N/A

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– I don't know

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The subject is not addressed though we might assume that there was such a distinction given the Roman context of the work.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: A generalized belief in the afterlife must be assumed for the writers and readers of this text, though it is not a primary object of attention.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– Field doesn't know

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Gods and semi-divine humans, such as Semiramis and her mother the fish-goddess Derketo, are present in the text.

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

Notes: There are gods and semi-divine humans in the universe of the text.

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– I don't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– I don't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– I don't know

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– I don't know

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– I don't know

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– I don't know

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– I don't know

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– I don't know

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– No

↳ In dreams?

– Yes

↳ In trance possession?

– I don't know

↳ Through divination practices?

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ Other?

– Specify: N/A

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– Yes

Notes: In the sense of a presumable hunger for veneration, but not literal physical hunger.

- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature
 - Specify: N/A

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

Notes: The text attests to syncretism between Greco-Roman and indigenous Semitic deities characteristic of the post-Hellenistic world.

- ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?
 - Yes

- ↳ Organized hierarchically?
 - Yes

- ↳ Power of beings is domain specific?
 - Yes

Notes: Yes, each god has a specific domains and sacred sites as far as is discernable.

- ↳ Other organization of pantheon?
 - Specify: N/A

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: Mixed human divine beings, such as the mythical Semiramis, are framed as primordial monarchs and givers of custom.

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be seen?
 - Yes

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be felt?
 - Yes

- ↳ Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living according to this text?
 - Yes

- ↳ In waking, everyday life?
 - Yes

- ↳ In dreams?
– No
- ↳ In trance possession?
– No
- ↳ Through divination practices?
– No
- ↳ Only through religious specialists?
– No
- ↳ Only through monarch?
– No
- ↳ Other?
– Specify: N/A

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: N/A

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Field doesn't know

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Notes: The text does not require castration but it describes and self-castration of the Galli without apparent moral judgement.

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– I don't know

Notes: It does not require anything, but it certainly describes.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– Yes

↳ Drama?

– Yes

↳ Comedy?

– Yes

↳ Tragedy?

– Yes

↳ Epic entertainment?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifice?

– Yes

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

↳ Suicide?

– No

↳ Bloodletting?

– No

↳ Mutilation?

– Yes

↳ Is self-sacrifice common and/or expected of elites?

– No

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– Yes

↳ Are they mandatory?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?

– Yes

↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings? (I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other?
– Specify: N/A

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?
– Yes

↳ By the community?
– I don't know

↳ By specific individuals?
– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?
– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Presumably the promulgation and circulation of the text was limited to a relatively privileged, literate stratum of society, but this cannot be known in full.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– I don't know

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– Yes

Notes: It is concerned with the construction and history of a particular temple complex

↳ Does the text advocate for public food storage?

– No

↳ Does the text provide guidance for food distribution?

– No

↳ Does the text regulate places for civic functions?

– No

↳ Does the text regulate places for the practice of justice?

– No

↳ Does the text advocate or specify controls for water management (irrigation, flood control)?

– No

↳ Does the text specify restrictions on common transportation?

– No

↳ Other form of regulation of public works?

– Specify: The text is not prescriptive but rather descriptive in terms of its approach to cultic practices at Hieropolis.

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: It mentions the military operations of the general Kombabus and his leadership of armies, but this is not necessarily treated in detail, and does not constitute a primary aspect of the text.

Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: De Dea Syria, Lightfoot, J.L. Lucian on the Syrian Goddess: Edited with Introduction and Translation. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2003.

Reference: De Dea Syria, Derven, Lucinda . "The Author of De Dea Syria and His Cultural Heritage". Numen 44, no. 2 (May 1997): 153-79.

Reference: De Dea Syria, Finglass, P.J.. "Autocastration or Regicide: Lucian, De Dea Syria, 20". The Classical Quarterly 55, no. 2 (December 2005): 629-32.